

A Novel Flavanol Glycoside from *Crotalaria prostrata* Rottl.

R. N. YADAVA* and ABHA SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Dr H. S. Gour University,
Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 30 May 1991, accepted 28 October 1991

THE medicinal value of the plant *Crotalaria prostrata* Rottl.¹ (N.O. Leguminosae) is said to be useful in derangements of the stomach and infantile diarrhoea.

Experimental

The plant material was supplied by United Chemicals and Allied Products (Calcutta) and authenticated by the Department of Botany, University of Sagar. A herbarium specimen (No. XXII) has been deposited in Natural Products Laboratory. Air-dried and powdered seeds were extracted with hot 95% EtOH. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a viscous mass and separated into water-soluble and -insoluble part. The water-soluble part was concentrated to a viscous mass (0.80%) and extracted successively with C₆H₆, CHCl₃, EtOAc, Me₂CO and MeOH.

The water-soluble part of the methanol-soluble fraction gave a single spot on tlc (Si-gel G; CHCl₃ - MeOH - H₂O, 13 : 7 : 2) on I₂ vapour as visualisation. It gave all the colour reactions of flavanoidal glycosides. It was purified by column chromatography (Si-gel G) to give a cream coloured crystalline solid (0.036%), C₃₇H₃₂O₁₇, m.p. 200-01° (Found : C, 59.53 ; H, 5.02. Calcd. for : C, 51.59 ; H, 5.09%), [α]_D²⁵ +30.7, [M]⁺ 628. It formed an acetyl derivative, C₄₃H₅₄O₂₈, m.p. 184-85° (Found : C, 53.90 ; H, 4.90. Calcd. for : C, 53.94 ; H, 4.95%) ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 280, 320sh, λ_{max} (NaOMe) 240, 330, 377sh, λ_{max} (AlCl₃) 292, 312, 340, 390sh, λ_{max} (NaOAc) 287, 362sh, λ_{max} (NaOAc + H₃BO₃) 265, 296sh, λ_{max} (AlCl₃ + HCl) 290, 310, 340, 354sh ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 332 (OH), 2 900, 1 680, 1 670, 1 452, 1 260, 1 125, 820 cm⁻¹ ; ¹H nmr (90 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) 5.20 (1H, d, J 9.9 Hz, C2), 6.72 (2H, d, J 7.0 Hz, C2', C6'), 6.88 (1H, d, J 6.5 Hz, C5'), 2.16 (3H, s, C3'-OAc), 2.18 (3H, s, C4'-OAc), 2.19 (3H, s, C5-

OAc), 5.80 (1H, s, C6), 2.12 (3H, s, C7-OAc), 5.90 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, C8), 4.32 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz, C1'' anomeric proton), 2.05 (3H, s, C2''-OAc), 2.14 (3H, s, C3''-OAc), 2.08 (3H, s, C4''-OAc), 4.10-4.60 (6H, m, protons of glucose), 4.42 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz, C1''' anomeric proton), 2.04 (3H, s, C2'''-OAc), 2.12 (3H, s, C3'''-OAc), 2.10 (3H, s, C4'''-OAc), 2.07 (3H, s, C6'''-OAc), 4.20-4.30 (6H, m, protons of galactose) ; [M]⁺ 628, m/z 465, 449, 304, 303, 276, 153, 152, 124.

The compound was hydrolysed with (7% ethanolic H₂SO₄) by refluxing for about 10 h and after removal of EtOH it yielded an aglycone, m.p. 238-39° (Found : C, 59.20 ; H, 3.90. Calcd. for : C, 59.25 ; H, 3.91%), [α]_D²⁵ +30.2, [M]⁺ 304. The hydrolysate neutralised with BaCO₃, BaSO₄ was filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. Pc examination (n-BuOH - HOAc - H₂O, 4 : 1 : 5) showed the presence of D-glucose and D-galactose (1 mol) (co-pc, co-tlc). The quantitative estimation of sugar in the hydrolysate confirmed the presence of one molecule of glucose and galactose.

The white crystalline microneedles (0.027%), C₃₅H₃₀O₇, m.p. 238-39° (Found : C, 59.20 ; H, 3.90. Calcd for : C, 59.25 ; H, 3.90%), [α]_D²⁵ +30.2, [M]⁺ 304, on tlc examination gave a single spot (R_f=0.69, CHCl₃ - MeOH - H₂O, 13 : 7 : 2) and was purified by column chromatography. It formed a penta-acetyl derivative, C₂₅H₂₂O₁₂, m.p. 225° (Found : C, 53.90 ; H, 4.90. Calcd for : C, 53.94 ; H, 4.95%), [M]⁺ 514, λ_{max} (MeOH) 287, 330sh, λ_{max} (NaOAc) 304, 324sh, λ_{max} (AlCl₃) 274, 325sh, λ_{max} (NaOMe) 260, 328, 345sh, λ_{max} (NaOAc + H₃BO₃) 263, 359sh ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 315, 2 904, 1 672, 1 670, 1 650, 1 284, 825 cm⁻¹ ; ¹H nmr (90 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) 5.20 (1H, d, J 9.9 Hz, C2), 6.72 (2H, d, J 7.0 Hz, C2', C6'), 2.16 (3H, s, C3'-OAc), 2.18 (3H, s, C4'-OAc), 6.88 (1H, d, J 6.5 Hz, C5') 2.20 (3H, s, C3-OAc), 2.19 (3H, s, C5-OAc), 5.80 (1H, s, C6), 2.17 (3H, s, C7-OAc), 5.92 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, C8), [M]⁺ 304, m/z 303, 276, 153, 152, 150, 125.

The glycoside was dissolved in MeOH and treated with sodium metaperiodate² for 5 days and the liberated HCOOH and the consumed periodate were estimated³.

The glycoside in EtOH was mixed with an equal volume of almond emulsion solution and left at 30° for 24 h. The examination of the hydrolysate on pc examination (n-BuOH - HOAc - H₂O, 4 : 1 : 5) showed the presence of β-linkage between the sugars as well as to the aglycone.

Results and Discussion

The water-soluble part of the methanol-soluble fraction gave a compound which showed all the colour reactions of the flavanoidal glycosides (1) and gave positive molisch test for glycoside and all the colour tests for flavanone⁴. Its acetyl derivative suggested the presence of eleven acetylysable OH

NOTES

groups. Compound **1** on acid hydrolysis gave an aglycone (**2**).

Compound **2** formed a penta-acetate, $C_{25}H_{32}O_{12}$. On KOH degradation, **2** gave phloroglucinol and protocatechuic acid (m.m.p., co-tlc), which confirmed the hydroxyl group at C5, C7, C3' and C4' positions⁵. A characteristic colour reaction with Zn/HCl⁶ and zirconium oxychloride in citric acid⁷ further confirmed the presence of OH group at C₃. Yellow fluorescence of the aglycone in uv light and the spectral shift with AlCl₃ of 60 nm relative to band-I in MeOH suggested a free OH group at C3 in the aglycone.

The signals for C2 appeared at δ 5.20 while the aromatic protons appeared at δ 6.72 (C2', C6') and 6.88 (C5'). The singlet at δ 5.80 was indicative of a proton at C6. ¹H nmr spectra of the acetyl derivative (**2**) showed a singlet at δ 2.16, 2.18, 2.19 and 2.11, indicative of the 3'-OAc, 4'-OAc, 5'-OAc and 7-OAc.

On permethylation⁸ followed by acid hydrolysis, gave 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose and confirmed that Cl of the glucose was attached at C3 of the aglycone which showed (1 $\rightarrow$ 6) linkage between D-galactose and D-glucose. Compound **1** on periodate oxidation also indicated the presence of disaccharide with both the sugars in pyranose form.

The emulsin enzymatic hydrolysis confirmed the presence of a β -linkage between the sugars and aglycone. Thus compound **1** was identified as taxifolin 3-*O*- β -D-galactopyranosyl (1 $\rightarrow$ 6)-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside.

- 1** ; R = Glc(1 $\rightarrow$ 6)Glu, R' = H
 (Glc- β -D-galactopyranosyl,
 Glu- β -D-glucopyranoside)
2 ; R = H, R' = H

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for various spectral analysis.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 81 ; K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Lalit Mohan Publication, Allahabad, 1935, Vol. I, p. 693.
2. E. L. HIRST and J. K. N. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1659.
3. S. RANGASWAMI and V. HARIHARAN, *Phytochemistry*, 1970, **9**, 409.
4. C. D. DOUGLASS, G. L. MORRIS and S. M. VENDEV, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4023, R. NEU, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1959, 292.
5. L. H. BRIGGS and R. H. LOCKER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2157.

6. J. C. FEW, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **10**, 3031.
7. R. COMERONI and A. SPADEV, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1956, **86**, 965.
8. R. KHUN, I. LOW and H. TRISCHMANN, *Angew. Chem.*, 1955, **67**, 32.